

REGIONAL TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE COMPONENT ELEMENTS AND FUNCTIONS

Janadilova Dinara Qalbay qizi

Kalbaeva Shirin Baxitbaevna

Master of Karakalpak state university

Among the structural elements that create the conditions for the sustainable development of the tourism sector and the stability of various branches of activity, the general infrastructure includes electricity and housing communications, roads, drinking water supply, various financial and economic organizations, insurance companies, and organizations. They are used as resources in the tourism sector, but without these resources, the tourism sector will not develop sufficiently.

It is known that in recent times in our country there is a tendency to classify special units of special importance that serve the infrastructure of the tourism sector in general infrastructure components. For example, the official documents of the legislative framework related to tourism, departments formed in insurance companies and organizations providing services for the development of tourism activities, effective and large-scale development of tourism exhibition activities for specialization, and increase of investment attractiveness in the field are related to the institutional infrastructure of tourism.

The special infrastructure in the market of tourist services consists of elements that are created, used, and create favorable conditions to provide services to tourists and includes them.

Figure 1. Interrelationship of structural elements of regional tourism infrastructure

They include natural resources created by human labor (vehicles, vehicles, entertainment complexes, museums, etc.) and natural resources created by nature (lakes, seas, rivers, mountains, forests, etc.). At the same time, the component of tourism infrastructure is diverse and consists of various tourist resources. The tourism infrastructure component includes all types of service elements and components for the implementation of tourist activities. In our opinion, as tourist resources, all resources that provide services that are useful to tourists and motivate them are relevant. The field of tourism is manifested as a social phenomenon that covers various forms of the implementation of tourist activities. Organizing and realizing various forms of tourist activity requires the formation of special components of the developed infrastructure.

Figure 2. Formation of tourism infrastructure by composition

According to him, in the development of business activities in the tourism industry, it is necessary to separate the tourism infrastructure into a special form, which is different in terms of structural formation and, accordingly, affects the process of increasing business activity in this field. Tourism infrastructure is formed in the following form (Figure 1.3).

It is one of the traditional components of general tourism, which is used for all forms of tourism that are not specific to a particular form of tourism. They include: vehicles (trains, planes, buses, etc.); means of accommodation (hotels, private means of accommodation, motels, etc.); such as common meals and recreational facilities are relevant.

The special infrastructure of tourism is a necessary condition for the realization of its specific forms and manifestations. For example, "for mountain-ski tourism, there should be equipment such as special ski tracks, lifts, skis. As long as, each type of tourism, it is possible to divide this type of tourism into infrastructure components of a traditional description, which provide the basic needs in its realization.

"The basic infrastructure ensures the creation of a variety of products. At this time, to attract tourists from the point of view of marketing, it is necessary to have special features of the offered product or additional product. To do this, it is possible to create a characteristic (additional, simultaneous) product for tourism infrastructure of this kind. For example, along with the development of skiing, it is necessary to have water parks and swimming pools around it. This concurrent non-featured infrastructure creates additional appeal and creates new motivations for travelers."

If we pay attention to the specific aspects and characteristics of the regional tourism market, depending on the type of tourists and consumers, tourist services can be classified into two main types: tourist services provided to domestic and foreign consumers. External (foreign) tourists are divided into outgoing and incoming tourists. Outgoing tourists means residents of our republic who go abroad as tourists. Incoming tourists are tourists from foreign countries.

REFERENCE

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